

Critical Stylistic Analysis of Select Twitter Users' Comments on the End to Special Anti-Robbery Squad's (ENDSARS) Protest in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates Twitter Users' comments on the end to special anti-robbery squad's (ENDSARS) protest in Nigeria. In a democratic society, protest is one of the legitimate and necessary ways individuals adopt to seek redress on issues that are neglected by the government hence the need to clearly discuss some linguistic features deployed online by commenters. This study therefore identifies some language features employed by commenters to express their thoughts and displeasure. It also discusses the socio-political implications of these comments in Nigeria. This was done in order to show how linguistic features in these comments show underlying meanings. The study employs both primary and secondary sources of data. The primary sources included fifteen comments selected from Twitter blog and adopted Jefferies 2007 Critical Stylistic as a theoretical framework. Secondary sources included books and journal articles. The study shows that Twitter users employed noun phrases, simple sentences and name calling as linguistic feature in achieving their aim. It therefore recommends that the Nigerian government should take citizens welfare seriously and that lives and property of the people should be secured.

KEYWORDS; Critical stylistics; ENDSARS; Protest; Twitter; Comments

INTRODUCTION

To have a society with no insecurities is mainly the aim of all ruling government and the hope of the citizens under the government. When there is a sense of discontent about a particular government from the citizens, criticisms and complaints begin and if these issues are ignored or not taken seriously by the government for a long time, the citizens might stage a protest against the government expressing their displeasure towards poor governance. Also, these discontents may be on issues concerning Human Rights, gender, ethnicity, economy, religion, justice and many more.

Every democratic society witnesses one form of social protest or the other. Social protest therefore is a kind of social and political expressions that bring about changes in society thereby affecting human behaviour, attitudes and knowledge as well as organizational' or institution's policies (Akpati, 2018). In a democratic society, protest has become an important way for communities to seek redress on issues that are neglected by the government.

Over the years, there have been numerous protests which have brought about unrest in the world today. Some of these protests would be mentioned here (The George Floyd protest of May 26, 2020, also known as Black Lives Matter, Arab Spring of 2010, ENDSARS Protest of October 10, 2020). Due to evolution, social protest has taken to the media as it gained great success in the 'Arab Spring' revolution. Thus, one of the protests afore-mentioned (ENDSARS Protest of 2020) is the main focus of this study.

Nigeria has had her own shares of protest starting from the resistance movement in the pre-colonial Era to full blown protest which grew into an international affair. All the movements tend to have similar themes such as corruption, injustice, poverty, brutality and insecurity. Hari (2014) supports that social movements are most of the time accompanied by general strikes. He for instance explains further that in Nigeria as in most developing countries of the world, citizens are often confronted with myriad of threats and social problems which are poverty, high rates of unemployment, violence, deprivation of resources, and lack of opportunities, marginalization and denial of freedom (Hari, 2014, p.33).

This study, therefore, clearly discusses ENDSARS Protest through the use of critical stylistics, a linguistic theory that focuses on how language tells the story of a society in form of social meaning (ideologies, reality, relationship and identity) (Olaluwoye, 2015). The study also shows how critical stylistic tools such as Naming and Describing, Negating, Assuming and Implying are used by commenters to show high level of corruption, injustice and insecurity in the country.

SOCIAL MEDIA DISCOURSE

Before the advent and development of the internet, discourse was carried out traditionally (face to face discourse), through print media, and spoken media (television and radio). Again, before the advent of social media, internet communication was basically by means of emails and texts on mobile phones. They were usually informal and made use of short phrases. In the 80's, social media was invented as internet relay chats. Other social media platforms such as Facebook (2004), YouTube (2005) and Twitter (2006) were invented. Social media according to Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) cited in Bardici (2012, p.1) is a set of internet based applications built on the technological foundation of Web 2.0. Bardici (2012) views social media as the promoter of modern day communication. People often share their ideologies on social media and their experiences. This view is supported by Jenkins *et al.* (2005) that social media makes people have a sense of connection with one another as they are able to share experiences and relate with such experiences.

The term media is a communication channel that is used to deliver data such as news, movies, education and other form of data to a large number of people. Media discourse is carried out in different forms depending on the branches of media itself which is made up of the print media and the broadcast media. O'Keffe (2013, p.411) therefore describes media discourse as interactions that take place through a broadcast platform, (spoken or written). This definition implies that participants of social media discourse are not present on a face to face conversation as it is traditionally done. According to Cotter and Perrin (2017, p.45), media discourse represents the social world.

REVIEW OF SOME RELEVANTS EARLIER STUDIES ON SOCIAL PROTESTS IN NIGERIA

Orji (2011) studies theme of marginalization of the Niger Delta region. He argues that the Niger Delta struggle against marginalization is fit to become a movement as it addresses injustice and demand change of socio-economic sector of the region. The study also discusses earlier movements made by people of the region against the subject matter.

Agbedo (2012) examines the linguistic messages of placards used during fuel subsidy removal protest in Nigeria. The study adopted quantitative method in its analysis and used Halliday's systemic functional grammar. The study shows how pent up emotions of the protesters were inscribed on placards and are grouped as; fuel subsidy removal, corruption, crash of public expectations/disappointment, governance and revolution (Agbedo, 2012, p.18).

Igwebuike *et al.* (2016) examine different online posts on fuel subsidy removal protest in Nigeria. A pragma-semiotic approach was adopted which helps to explain both verbal and nonverbal modes used in portraying people and their actions. Findings of the study clearly reveal different visuals and pragmatic strategies such as prayer, negative, labelling, humour, mockery, abuse and fierce appeal were mainly used by the protesters. The study therefore concludes that an awareness of verbal-visual posts is very important in understanding and interpreting the socio-political issues in Nigeria.

Hari (2014) investigates social media and its impact on the occupy Nigeria protest. Findings of the work show that social media assisted in coordinating and mobilizing social actions and also gave the protest a wide exposure. In achieving this, the study made use of quantitative analysis approach. Adekalu *et al.* (2015) work on social mobilization and the implications for cross cultural research with the bring-back-our-

girls campaign. The study focuses mainly on the role diverse cultures played in influencing the outcome of some social movements that have gone global. It adopted content analysis method. Findings of the research also reveal that despite the differences in geographical area, religion, culture, beliefs, the people still have the same mutual understanding as they share the same suffering, despair and sadness. The study therefore recommends that public enlightenment on social media mobilization is important; the social mobilization processes, progress and performance should be monitored regularly in order to achieve positive changes.

Egbunike (2015) carries out a comparative study between social media and the framing of occupy Nigerian protest in selected Nigerian newspapers in 2012. In comparing two media outlets, their study shows that newspapers headlines might not project the ideologies of a social protest because of their choice of words. Findings of the study reveal that diagnosis, motivation and prognosis were better framed in newspapers than other social media platforms. Similarly, Chilwa (2015) investigates different Facebook posts on the removal of fuel subsidy in Nigeria. Findings show that different language strategies like code-switching, local pidgin were mainly used by protesters to express their displeasure towards the removal of fuel subsidy in Nigeria.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Critical Stylistics

Critical stylistics is a fusion of pure stylistics and critical discourse analysis. Stylistics is one of the branches in applied linguistics which focuses on the study of style in texts especially but not exclusively in literary works. Wales (1990) states that stylistics is not just an aspect of linguistics that describes features in texts but used to analyse features across texts' functional significance and interpretations, thereby, relating to their linguistic effects and causes. On the other hand, critical discourse analysis is an analytical approach that critically describes, interprets and explains ways in which discourse a constructed, maintained and legitimized inequality in language. This definition explains that language is a tool used socially and CDA simply interprets the underlying meaning in a discourse in different contexts beyond the surface level.

Critical stylistics is credited to Jefferies (2007). Jefferies designed C.S to function on ideologies. To Jefferies, all kinds of texts, whether political texts, poems and other forms of language use have meaning and reveal a given ideology (Jefferies, 2010). C.S answers questions like what text means, does and how it does it. Critical

stylistics is modeled after Halliday's meta functions of language (interpersonal, textual and ideational). Jefferies 2010 further adds that critical stylistics helps to bring together the main general functions that a text has in representing, which is based on the fact that there is a level at which texts organize the world we experience. He also classifies critical stylistics interpretation of a text meaning in two ways; (a) textual method (b) contextual method. The textual method derives its meaning from the structure of a text. It has no concern or connection with the context or situation where a text is being produced. The contextual method focuses mainly on how a text producer makes use of his linguistic choices in a particular context to represent his reality. This is in line with Mahmoud (2018) who sees critical stylistics as a structure that pays attention to some linguistic features used in a discourse. C.S has the following analytical tools; (a) Naming and Describing (b) Representing Actions/Events/States (c) Equating and Contrasting (d) Exemplifying and Enumerating (e) Prioritising (f) Assuming and Implying (g) Negating (Jefferies, 2010).

Naming and Describing

This tool shows that there are different ways a text can describe the world. Naming and describing includes choice of nouns, modification through pre-modification and post modification. This means that noun phrases are constructed which consists of the head-word and accompanied by pre or post modifying elements.

Representing Actions/Events/States

This is simply a speaker's choice of verb. A speaker is able to represent the same event in different ways. This level uses transitivity.

Equating and Contrasting

These tools refer to the use of similar constructions as it is represented by equating and opposite construction. These tools represent events by looking for equivalences or opposites. Equating or opposition meaning make use of markers such as coordinating and subordinating conjunctions (AND, OR, BUT, BECAUSE, IF, UNLESS etc)

Exemplifying and Enumerating

This involves a general categorization and examples; most often enumerating a long list of the member of a category.

Prioritizing

This focuses on the grammatical arrangements in prioritizing comments or information over others, focusing on transformational choices and subordination (Iman, 2020). This tool constructs a clause in reference to an event or entity in their order of importance.

Assuming and Implying

These tools show if certain knowledge in a text is background information or an implied one. Assuming and implying are tools used to communicate one's ideologies. The tool allows readers to make their own meaning from the information given by reading in between the lines.

Negating

A text producer uses this tool to create a view of a world that does not or is not possible to come into existence by using negating words like 'not', 'never'.

Hypothesizing

This tool refers to the process by which the text producer does not always provide the view of the world as it is. It shows the degree of certainty in a speaker's texts about an idea or proposition. Here modality is used (would, should, shall. Will, ought to).

Speech and Thoughts of Others

This tool is employed in order to embed people's interpretations on others without having to be faithful to the speech. In representing speech or thoughts of others, different categories of speech are used as direct, reported and indirect speech.

METHODOLOGY

This paper adopted availability sampling technique method. This is basically used to select comments suitable for any given analysis from the vast array of data. The data were sourced from the Internet and were selected from Twitter blogs. The comments are the reactions of Nigerians to the ENDSARS protest (2020). The criterion used for the selection of these data from Twitter is based on the fact that Twitter was the main base of the ENDSARS Nigerian online protesters. It was also selected because of its strong use in mobilizing protesters during the protest. A total of thirty comments were selected for analysis. The reason for this restriction is to carry out an indepth analysis of language features used by commenters and discuss their implications. The data were analyzed using Jefferies Critical Stylistics. Though, there are different tools in critical stylistics that can be used for data analysis, only three of the tools were used in this study: Naming and Describing, Negating, Assuming and Implying.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

This section focuses on data presentation and analysis. Analysis in this section is divided into three: Naming and Describing, Negating and Assuming and Implying.

Data Presentation on Naming and Describing

The concepts above are used to describe a situation or events using nominal items or groups. The use of these items give the reader a view or picture of how the speaker sees unfolding events in a given discourse.

NOUN PHRASES

Examples:

Nigeria is literally **The wild wild west**

Example 2:

It is high time we seize the mantle from **the Aged** and so called **MEN IN POWER**

Example 3:

... **These old men** need to take a chill pill. **The future** belongs to us

Data Analysis on Naming and Describing (Noun Phrases)

The comment in example 1 is a noun phrase with MH structure. 'the' and 'wild wild' are modifying elements and 'west' is the headword. Wild denotes untamed, feral fierce etc. The commenter names the referent, Nigeria the 'the wild west' which means a country filled with horror, with no law or justice. Example 2 shows two nominal groups: 'the Aged' (MH) and 'men in power' (HQ) nominal structures. The commenter describes Nigerian leaders as aged which is synonymous to old fashioned, myopic, unbending to new ideas and goes ahead to name them 'men in power' thus representing them as leaders who are not capable but forced their way to the position of authority. The noun phrases 'these old men' and 'the future' in example 3 have MH nominal structure. Present Nigerian politicians are described as old men while the youth are referred to as 'the future'. The two phrases show the political state of Nigeria where old men rule and do not give any political opportunity to the younger generation in Nigeria.

Name Calling

This is an abusive or provocative word or expression mainly used by people to slur, and discredit others. It can as well be used to incite people to violence or cause an unhealthy atmosphere. Examples from the data are presented below:

- Example 4 **Inconsiderate beggars**
- Example 5 **Wolves**
- Example 6 **block-hearted** people
- Example 7 **Wicked** leaders....
- Example 8 **Heartless** and **greedy** leaders...

Example 4, 'inconsiderate beggars' is used to reveal the attitude of politicians and describe them as insensitive. The word 'wolves' in example 5 is a large wild animal of the dog families that live and hunt in packs. Thus wolves are predators that go after their preys. The action of the predators (wolves) in this context is killing, shooting and harassment of peaceful protesters. 'block-hearted' in example 6 is a compound word and connotes an imagery of a difficult person.

The commenter therefore describes the Anti-ENDSARS protesters as people without human feelings. This can also be seen in example 7 and 8; 'wicked leaders' and 'heartless and greedy leaders' respectively. The name calling by commenters are responses or reactions of citizens who are protesting the bad governance of the country by its political leaders.

Data Presentation on Negating

As the name implies, negation brings about the absence of something in an event or situation. When a speaker applies the concept of negation, he/she implants a view of a world or an event that is impossible to exist. This is achieved with the use of negative prefixes and suffixes such as 'un', 'il', 'less' etc. Some examples are presented below:

Example 9:

Never heard of a protest being banned by a government

Example 10: by that they won't be **jobless** and have access to guns and ammunition

Example 11: I feel so **helpless**

The speaker employs negation in relation to the happenings during the protest. These linguistic items include the grammatical word 'not' as a whole in its contrasted form, negative adverbs such as bare, never etc and affixes and suffixes. Commenters use these critical stylistic tools to evoke a positive or negative feeling in their minds about the Nigerian government. The negative adverb 'never' in example 9 connotes the absence of the possibility that a governor should stop a peaceful protest, as protest is one of the basic human rights in every democratic society. Also, the comment in example 10 is a negative expression. The word 'jobless' is a negative word which shows the high rate of unemployment in the country. In example 11, the negated word 'helpless' shows injustice and corruption in the country as expressed by the commenter. This is linked to the killings, torture and subjugation experienced by the citizens. All the negated items thus expressed a sense of lack and want.

Data Presentation of Assuming and Implying

This tools show if certain knowledge in a text is background information or an implied one in texts. These tools are based on what the speaker implies and what the listener assumes out of the discourse.

Example 12:

We won't keep silent anymore...

Example 13:

We gave them all the power. Our first mistake but the whole world has made that mistake

Example 14: different sectors of government have been tackled ... these few days

Example 15: Armoured tanks that couldn't be deployed to Sambisa forest to fight the Boko Haram insurgents in almost a decade are being used to murder peaceful protesters

Data Analysis of Assuming and Implying

In example 12, the expression 'we won't keep silent anymore' is an independent clause in which its modal verb is negated thus showing absence of or lack of an action. With the presence of the contracted modal verb 'won't', the sentence reveals the attitude of the protesters and how they are being treated. The clause also implies that Nigerians have now risen to fight injustice and corruption.

Another form of implying and assuming is in example 13 while attention will be focused on 'our first mistake'. The commenter uses the pronominal item 'our' to represent the entire Nigerians. 'First mistake' here implies how those in government were first selected or elected to govern them. The comment generally depicts the commenter's state of regret and wrong choices made in choosing their leaders. Also, the noun phrase 'these few days' in example 14, presupposes that the ENDSARS peaceful protest was a huge success within a short period of time. The word that

presupposes that the Nigerian government is incapacitated, not proactive is the contracted not' in the modal verb 'could in example 15 used to form the verb phrase 'couldn't be deployed'. This also indicates failure of government to protect her citizens.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study has clearly shown how the selected analytical tools of critical stylistics were used to explain Twitter Users' comments during the end special anti-robbery squad's protest among Nigerians in 2020. To this end, three analytical tools were used in this study. Findings showed that naming and describing were used to slur and degrade government officials. It was also used as an effective way to express their anger and displeasure towards the Nigerian government. It was also observed that assuming and implying reveal commenters' hidden message (s) in their comments. They implied a presupposed fact and left the readers to make more meaning out of it.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATION

This study focused mainly on the analysis of Twitter Users' comments on the end special anti-robbery squad protest among Nigerians. These comments depict some underlying ideologies and the linguistic features show some level of corruption, insecurity and injustice. The critical stylistic tools adopted in this study made it possible for readers to identify and bring out the deeper meanings in the selected twitter users' comments.

It therefore recommends that the Nigerian government should always take the welfare of her citizens seriously in order to avoid future protests. Also, lives and property of the people should be paramount to the government.

REFERENCES:

- Agbedo, C.U. (2012). Placards as a language of civil protest in Nigeria: A systemic-functional analysis of fuel subsidy crisis. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (JHSS)*, 6(2), 17-26
- Akpati, C.F. (2018). Multimodal critical discourse analysis of selected Nigerian protest videos (2012-2015), An Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria.
- Bardici, M. V. (2012). A discourse analysis of the media representation of social media for change: The case of Egyptian revolution and political change. Thesis submitted for completion of Master of communication for development, Malmo University, Sweden.
- Chiluwa, I. (2015). "Occupy Nigeria": A critical discourse analysis of Facebook posts in the fuel subsidy removal protests *CLINA*, 1(1), 47-69
- Egbunike, N. (2015). Framing the occupy Nigeria protests in newspapers and social media. *Open Access Library Journal*. 2(5) 1-13.
- Igwebuike, E., Abioye, T. & Chimuanya, L. (2016). A pragmatic-semiotic analysis of "occupy Nigeria group" online posts on the 2012 fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria. *Journal of Visual Literacy*, 35(3), 201
- Iman, M.O.A, Salih, M. (2020). A critical stylistic analysis of equivocation in a religious text. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(3), 4800-4805.
- Jefferies, L. (2007). *Textual construction of the female body: A critical discourse approach*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Jefferies, L. (2010a). *Critical stylistics*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Jenkins, H., Puroshodma, R. (2015). *Confronting the challenge of participatory culture: Media education for the 21st century*. ----- MIT Press.

Kaplan, A.M & Haenlien, M. (2010). Users of the world unite! The challenges and the opportunities social media. *Business Horizons*, 53(1), 59-68.

Mahmoud, A.M. (2018). The ideologies of war and social class in Atmemeri: A critical stylistic analysis. *Prague Journal of English Studies*, 7(1), 161-184.

O'keeffe, A. (2013). Media and discourse analysis in Gee, J. & Handford, M. (Eds). *The Routledge Handbook of Discourse Analysis*. London: Routledge, pp. 441-454.

Olaluwoye, L. (2015). A critical stylistic analysis of the identity of minority groups in the Nigerian print media. *Journal of Literature, Languages and Linguistics*, 16, 87-93.

Wales, K. (1990). *A dictionary of stylistics*, Routledge: New York